

A NOTE ON THE PREPARATION OF β -4-METHOXY-1-NAPHTHOYLPROPIONIC ACID.

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A recent publication of Fieser and Hershberg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2314) renders it unnecessary to continue the work we have been doing since last July. The results already obtained are recorded below.

Ruzicka and Waldmann (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, 15, 907) first obtained β -4-methoxy-1-naphthoylpropionic acid by condensing α -naphthol methyl ether with succinic anhydride in presence of aluminium chloride using carbon disulphide as the solvent. As the yields by this method were not good (30-40%) we investigated this reaction using different solvents and obtained 40% yield by the use of petroleum ether and 90-92% yield by using either nitrobenzene or acetylene tetrachloride as the solvents. β -4-Methoxy-1-naphthoylpropionic acid has been characterised by the preparation of methyl ester (m.p. 56°) and an ethyl ester (b.p. 230°/15 mm.). The constitution of the acid has been further confirmed by its synthesis by the action of succinic anhydride on the Grignard reagent prepared from 4-bromo-1-methoxynaphthalene.

EXPERIMENTAL.

To a boiling suspension of succinic anhydride (4 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.) was added the Grignard reagent prepared from 4-bromo-1-methoxy-naphthalene (8 g.), magnesium (1.5 g.) ether (50 c.c.) and a crystal of iodine. It was warmed for half an hour on a water-bath, decomposed by ice and dilute sulphuric acid. The ether-benzene layer was once washed with water and then extracted with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate. On acidifying the sodium carbonate extract a greenish solid separated (2.5 g.), which on crystallisation from methyl alcohol melted at 172°. It did not depress the m.p. of β -4-methoxy-1-naphthoylpropionic acid.

Methyl β -4-methoxy-1-naphthoylpropionate, prepared by esterifying the acid with methyl alcohol, is soluble in benzene, ethyl acetate and hot methyl alcohol, and melted at 56°. (Found: C, 68.28; H, 5.7. $C_{16}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 68.43; H, 5.67 per cent).

Ethyl β -4-methoxy-1-naphthoylpropionate had b.p. 230°/15 mm. (Found: C, 71.21; H, 6.29. $C_{17}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 71.32; H, 6.29 per cent).